

Significantly exaggerated carrier mobilities are reported in: Huihui Zhu, Ao Liu, Kyu In Shim, Jisu Hong, Jeong Woo Han, and Yong-Young Noh, “High-Performance and Reliable Lead-Free Layered-Perovskite Transistors”, *Adv. Mater.* **32**, 2002717 (2020) DOI: 10.1002/adma.202002717.^{1,*}

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The charge carrier mobilities of perovskite thin-film transistors (TFTs) reported in this paper by H. Zhu *et al.* are found to be grossly overestimated. The actual mobility of the best (“champion”) device, correctly calculated from the presented data, is $\mu_{\text{sat}} \sim 0.5 \text{ cm}^2\text{V}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$, not $3.5 \text{ cm}^2\text{V}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$ as claimed by the authors. Thus, the main conclusion of the paper regarding the realization of “high-performance perovskite transistors” appears to be misleading.

The following device parameters are given in the paper (mostly in Supplementary):

Channel width, $W = 1000 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$;
Channel length, $L = 200 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$;
 SiO_2 gate dielectric thickness, $d_{\text{ox}} = 100 \text{ nm}$.

Other parameters used in the analysis below:

The gate-channel capacitance per unit area for a 100 nm-thick SiO_2 dielectric layer is $C_i = 34.5 \text{ nF/cm}^2$.²

1. The best performing (“champion”) transistor.

This TFT is shown in the paper by the red curves on Figs. 2d and 4a (the red curves of these Figs. are the same curve). The authors report that this device exhibits the highest saturation regime mobility, $\mu_{\text{sat}} = 3.5 \text{ cm}^2\text{V}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$. The Fig. on the right is the transfer characteristic of this TFT digitized (small blue dots).

The Fig. below shows this very transfer curve, replotted as a linear $|I_{\text{DS}}|^{0.5}(V_{\text{GS}})$ plot (solid lines), and its derivative, $\delta(|I_{\text{DS}}|^{0.5})/\delta V_{\text{GS}}$ (dotted lines), which is used to calculate the saturation mobility according to the standard Shockley equation:²

$$\mu_{\text{sat}} = \frac{2L}{WC_i} \cdot \left(\frac{\partial \sqrt{|I_{\text{DS}}|}}{\partial V_{\text{GS}}} \right)^2.$$

Fig. 4a red curve (the same curve as in Fig. 2d)

The "champion" device (Fig. 2d)

The same formula was said to be used by H. Zhu *et al.* in their paper. The saturation regime mobility correctly calculated from these data is about $\mu_{\text{sat}} \approx 0.53 \text{ cm}^2\text{V}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$. The correct calculation involves using the most linear region of the transfer curves, far from non-linear subthreshold or near-threshold regions. Thus, in this calculation, the derivative was averaged over the range $-30 \text{ V} < V_{\text{GS}} < 0$ (shown above by the dotted green line) and between the right-to-left and left-to-right V_{GS} sweep directions.

2. Alternatively, one can fit the transfer curves of the “champion” TFT with the conventional field-effect transistor model (the Shockley model). In this process, we should bear in mind that the threshold (onset) voltage of these devices is noticeably shifted to the right (perhaps, due to a self-doping), and, thus, a part of the transfer curve at high negative V_{GS} is outside of the saturation regime. The Fig. below shows the result of such a complete model fit, which uses the mobility and threshold voltage as fitting parameters. The fit is performed for both branches of the transfer curve corresponding to the right-to-left and left-to-right V_{GS} sweep directions. The saturation mobility obtained from this fit is consistent with the mobility calculated above by taking the average derivative. **Both methods give the mobility within $\mu_{\text{sat}} \sim 0.5 - 0.6 \text{ cm}^2\text{V}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$.**

The "champion" device (Fig. 2d)

3. The transfer characteristics of these TFTs are highly non-linear. Given the obviously non-linear character of these TFTs, the most reliable way of evaluating their carrier mobility would still be taking the most linear curve out of all available curves and using it to determine its average slope. The result of such an evaluation is shown in the Fig. below (green dashed line). **Again, it shows that the most realistic mobility of these devices (here, we are still considering the champion TFT) is $\sim 0.5 \text{ cm}^2\text{V}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$.**

The "champion" device (Fig. 2d)

4. Finally, below we perform an analogous analysis of another device (their 2nd best?) presented on Fig. 2c of the paper. The analysis shows that the real mobility of this TFT is about $\mu_{\text{sat}} \sim 0.1 - 0.13 \text{ cm}^2\text{V}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$. The plots below are self-explanatory, and the resultant realistic mobilities are indicated on the plots.

Another device (Fig. 2c),

$$\mu_{\text{sat}} \sim 0.13 \text{ cm}^2\text{V}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$$

CONCLUSION:

The charge carrier mobilities of perovskite TFTs reported in the paper by H. Zhu *et al.*¹ appear to be severely exaggerated. The correctly calculated mobilities are within $\mu_{\text{sat}} \sim 0.12 - 0.66 \text{ cm}^2\text{V}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$, which means that the reported mobilities are overestimated by a factor of 5 - 30.

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